

4th International Conference on Materials Science and Engineering (MSE 2020)

October 24 - 25, 2020, Dubai, UAE

<https://cse2020.org/mse/index.html>

Scope

4th International Conference on Materials Science and Engineering (MSE 2020) will provide an excellent international forum for sharing knowledge and results in theory, methodology and applications impacts and challenges of Materials Science and Engineering. The conference documents practical and theoretical results which make a fundamental contribution for the development of Materials Science and Engineering. The aim of the conference is to provide a platform to the researchers and practitioners from both academia as well as industry to meet and share cutting-edge development in the field.

Topics of Interest

- Art Conservation Science
- Biomaterials, tissue engineering
- Ceramics
- Composites
- Corrosion
- Diffraction studies)
- Energy
- Fracture of materials
- Magnetic Materials
- Materials for Electronics and Photonics
- Materials Synthesis & Processing
- Materials Theory, Computation, and Design
- Mechanical Properties
- Metals and Alloys
- Nanomaterials, Nanoparticulates and Nanocomposites
- Polymers
- Self-Assembly
- Solar Energy
- Surfaces and Interfaces

Paper Submission

Authors are invited to submit papers through the conference [Submission system](#) by **July 26, 2020**. Submissions must be original and should not have been published previously or be under consideration for publication while being evaluated for this conference. The proceedings of the conference will be published by as a Special Issue in the [International Journal of Advances in Materials Science and Engineering \(IJAMSE\)](#).

Important Dates

- **Submission Deadline : July 26, 2020**
- Authors Notification : September 11, 2020
- Registration & Camera-Ready Paper Due : September 19, 2020

Contact Us

Here's where you can reach us : mse@csen2020.org (or) mseconference@yahoo.com